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Unsung Heroes of Jharkhand Santhal Pargana: A Brief Study of Glorious Past From 1830-1947 And A Need To revisit Regional History

Vinay Kumar Hind*

Abstract

This research paper is a brief overview of some of the unsung heroes and freedom fighters who were more than a mere unsatisfied disgruntled revolutionary. The paper is quantitative, descriptive, and exploratory research at the same time. This work is based on primary and secondary sources and some interviews of prominent figures of Santhal pargana having field experience on the topic. Along with this I have mentioned some of the forgotten names with their brief contribution to the Indian National Movement in general and to secure the traditional rights for the tribal's in particular. This paper can be seen as a small attempt to study various Indian important events of the Indian freedom struggle that occurred on the soil of Jharkhand.

Also, this work is an argumentative move towards pointing out the biased done by British authorities and colonial writers during pre-independence

India and the marginalized space given to Jharkhandi's by mainstream historians in the post-independence era. This paper contains a larger canvas of Jharkhand's contributions during the British era and post-Independence times.

Introduction of Jharkhand: Jharkhand is the 28th state of India and ranked 16th in area and 14th largest by population. Ranchi is its capital and Hindi as its official language. Founded on 15th of November 2000, after a long struggle for separate state. Beside Hindi, Urdu is its second state language.

Main research question: The main research question is that in the latter part of the paper we will see that Jharkhand's area, role and virtue was so vast during Ancient, Medieval and Modern period but despite that only some of the few National level leaders from this area came into limelight. A majority of freedom fighters were either ignored or given a small place by colonial writers or the mainstream academia in post-Independence era. This paper is a small move to recognize those young Jharkhandi blood's who blindly followed the ideologies of both the wings of Congress and also the revolutionaries.

Also, One of the Prime focus of this work is to High light the different perceptions' that was Tagged by different colonial mind-set to the valour of Jharkhandi people and marginalized there efforts only to the limits of regional history. For example, Preindependence Jharkhandi revolts were seen as mere agrarian revolt no less no more, mostly by colonial Administrative writers pointing out towards few agrarian revolts like Pahadiya Revolt. During post independence- main stream academia and historian only seen it as Unsatisfied land and rights related movement and political leaders saw it as a fight of

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insider vs outsider for their on motives, which can be seen as ongoing current stunts on 1932 khatian issue.

*Note- Now I am discussing the Jharkhand status, territorial vastness, and political kingdoms in brief to get an insight that how enlightened this area was since ancient time, but very little justice was done with its people and their history.

Jharkhand During Ancient period: The description of Jharkhand is also found in Vedic books, *Vayu puran* Jharkhand is called *Murand* and In *Vishnu puran* It is referred as *Mund*. The Chota Nagpur region was known as *Pundrik* during Mahabharata period. In some Buddhist text there's the description of the Chinese traveller Fahien coming to India in 399 BC, Fahien has called Chota Nagpur as *Kukkulad* in his book. And in early medieval Sanskrit literature Chota Nagpur has been called *Kalind desh*.

Jharkhand During Medieval period: The use of word Jharkhand for the tribal areas of Chhota Nagpur first started in the medieval period itself. Its first use was in a copper plate of 13th century. In this period, it was organised as a separate land block. In the medieval period, Chhota Nagpur was the Kingdom of many small Hindu and semi-

Hindu rulers, among which the Nagwani's of kokra, the Singhvans of Raxel, Singhbhum of Palamu and the Man dynasty of Manbhum were prominent.

13th century was important for the Chota Nagpur region because, in 1206 AD Bakhtiyar khilji attacked Nadia via Jharkhand. During Iltutmish and Balban, Jharkhand remained undisturbed because of Nagavansi ruler Hari Karan was powerful and influential. Firoz Shah Tughlaq attacked Hazaribag and one Satgaon and the adjacent area. And he made Satgaon as capital of the won territory. Later Tughlaq of

Delhi were not able to move forward, due to the heavy and strong resistance from Nagvansi ruler.

According to Tujuk-I-Jahangiri in 1615-16 Ibrahim Khan attacked and captured sankh river which was famous for Diamond. During the attack the ruler was Raja Durjan Sal and send to Gwalior Fort as prisoner. After 12-year Jahangir release him and gave his territory on leases of 6000 annually and also give him the title of "Shahi".

During the time of Aurangzeb, the struggle of the Mughals in Jharkhand was mainly with the Chero kings. Which lasted till the death of Aurangzeb.

Jharkhand During Modern period: The first entry of the British into Jharkhand was from Singhbhum. In this region, Dhalbhum of Pala kings, Porhat of Singh king and Kolhan state of Ho people had special importance. In January 1767, Ferguseon was sent to attack Singhbhum to collect regular taxes from these states and to keep them under his suzerainty. The British captured the Ghatshila palace on 22 March 1767. In 1768, Jagannath Dhal revolted against the British, which is known as the Dhal rebellion. It is considered the first successful revolt of Jharkhand. In 1820 Major Rafsej entered the Kolhan region. Be on the banks of the Roro River and fought in the British army, in which the British were victorious. In 1821 AD, under the leadership of Colonel Richard, the English army entered the area. After a struggle that lasted for a month, the Ho people accepted the subordination of the company. The Ho people actively participated in the Kol Rebellion of 1831-32. He helped Ganga Narayan Singh and the Chuhad rebels in every way. 1836 AD On the advice of T S Wilkinson, an English army entered Kolhan. After about 4 months of struggle, the Ho people surrendered in February 1837 AD. And they were ready to pay taxes directly to the company. In 1837AD, the Kolhan region was made a new administrative unit and placed

under the British authority. In this way, only after 72 years of getting Diwani by the East India Company, the Kolhan area or as such, Jharkhand could be established.

After slowly establishing a foothold in Jharkhand, the British gradually started to dominate Palamu. In 1771, Camac took control of Palamu. At that time the ruler of Palamu was Raja Chitrajit Rai of Chero. Chero Raja Chitrajit Rai and Thakurai Jainath Singh fled to Ramgarh. In April 1772 there was a war between Jainath Singh and Thomas the Scout and the British army was defeated. In this battle, Sergeant Pelvin was killed, while Scout was wounded in the leg. The fort of Ranka and Jainath Singh bravely captured it back. When Camac again reached Kunda with a large army, Jainath Singh left Palamu in 1772 and went to some unknown place. It is believed that they had migrated to the Giridih forests, as some local research suggests, (Umesh Kumar *Secretary Jharkhand Research Institute, Deoghar)* Thus the British established the suzerainty on Palamu.

At the time of the British's entry into Chotanagpur Khas, the Nagvanshi king here was Dripnath Shahi. In the Hazaribagh area, the British had to face the most from the side of Ramgarh state. Raja Mukund Singh of Ramgarh continued to face the British from beginning to end. The entry of the British in Hazaribagh was led by Captain Camac. Ramgarh was attacked in 1772 AD. Mukund Singh fled to Panchet. Tej Singh was declared the new king. In 1773 AD, Ramgarh district was formed by merging Ramgarh, Palamu and Chotanagpur.

Santhal Parganas and British Rule: The Santhal pargana was part of the ancient Anga kingdom. This area was earlier known as *Jungle Terai*. In 1592 AD, Rajmahal was made the capital of Bengal. It remained as the capital of Bengal till 1660. Here the advance of the British took place before the battle of Buxar. This trading agency was established by the British in 1676. Maratha occupied the Rajmahal area in 1742. In 1757 AD Sirajudaula reached the palace after being defeated in the battle of Palasi. As a result of the victory of Major Adams against Mir Qasim in 1763 AD, the Company's monopoly on the Rajmahal area was established.

Jharkhand revolt: More than the peasant revolt and fight of insider vs outsider

Till now, I believe that a kind of misinterpretation and misunderstanding was developed by most of academician, that the revolts within Jharkhand was mere a peasant's revolt and a fight for their own interest. But some facts and data indicate that it's not so true. As India was fighting to push the British out from Indian soil because the land belongs to Indians. In the same way the people of Jharkhand are fighting to push the agents of big Zamindar and British out of the Jharkhand territory to protect their land rights and freedoms along with their culture and tradition, they fought for cultural independence till 1906. But after 1908, with the expansion of Congress and later under Gandhian leadership people got united to fight against one common enemy that is Britisher's. And in this unification not only the national leaders but regional leaders like Hari Shankar vyasji, Niani Gopal Mukherji Soma Bhagat, Lalla Bhagat, Bajrang Sahay, Vinod Anand Jha and others helped to very large extend.

Prima- facie its looks that most of the historians believed from the Kol, Ho, Bhumij rebellions etc are the result of dissatisfaction of peasants and land rights issue and popularized the same by many colonial writers like Thomson in his book "*Rise and Fulfilment of British Rule in India*". One of the major issues with Jharkhand history is that during pre-independence era colonial mindset authors tried to show the fight against foreign

rule as only a peasant's issue. And after Independence the irony was that most of the mainstream academicians either followed the earlier style of writing or wrote only about National leaders of freedom struggle and their visit to Jharkhand belt and tagged as an Unsatisfied land rights movement. Contemporary time it has been seen as a fight of insider versus outsider.

The British established their foothold in important parts of Jharkhand by 1767-68. There were tremendous reasons behind the discontent of the Jharkhand local tribe to fight against foreign rule. When I say foreign rule then it consists of all the ruling power outside the territory of Jharkhand of the time including Maratha, Afghan rulers and Britisher's as well.

The local tribes believed that foreign rule in general is harmful for their culture and rights. Besides this threat the other reason for discontent was famine of 1770, 1777 and 1800 and various economic inequalities as opined by *S. B. Choudhry in "Civil Disturbances During the British Rule in India"*. He opined that *Kol insurrection was the culmination of the people's grievances such as over excess of taxes, bribery in judiciary and administration, Collection of heavy interests by moneylenders*. Regarding Bhumij revolt led by Ganga Narain Singh it is believed that this was occurred due to the excess brutalities of the local king and outsiders, but to many extents this also took place due to the excess of taxation by British official. And this created a base for the pre-congress organization to stand against British domination. As Jagdish Chandra Jha rightly observed that Ganga narain hangama was an example of popularist movement which was aimed at creating an ideal world in which there was no exploitation. This symbolises the ideas of French revolution to many extents. Nature of Bhumij revolt is one example of such partial study done by colonial writers there are many more revolts which was not mere a peasant revolt.

One of the drastic changes that occurred due to the entry of Britisher's on Indian soil as ruler was commodification of land, fixation and transfer of land rights, commercialization of agriculture etc. Due to this the traditional land rights of Jharkhand tribes and inhabitant was sacrificed. To a large extent this forced them to believe that alien rule will always be a threat to their identity and livelihood. This thought process was not sudden it took many decades facing the attack of Marathas, Afghan rulers, and apparently with British as well.

Jharkhand, Jharkhandi and National Freedom struggle: Slowly and gradually the local tribes of Jharkhand and sadan people were become familiar with the administration of British and at some places with the cruel rule of agents of Britishers. But still there are some many examples being available which shows that still the dissatisfaction was widespread like Santhal revolt (1856) just before the 1857 revolt can be seen as predecessor of that brave act. Most importantly Sardari agitation popularly known as '*Mulki larai*' (the struggle for land) was running in the background of Birsa Munda movement. Both the acts to fight back for their land and traditional rights can be seen as preparatory stage for the upcoming national struggle for independence. Briefly Sardar movement was happened in three phases *agrarian (1858), revivalist (1881-1890) and political (1890-1895-96)*. Beside this the 1857 revolt filled the gap of fire among the Jharkhand people and the message was spread to many parts of Jharkhand. Especially at Ranchi the British might was tested very badly. The sepoys of Ramgarh battalion mutinied against the British under the able leadership of Madho Singh. Many documents proves that the Ranchi revolt was supported strongly by

Vishwanath Shahdeo and Pande Ganpat Rao. There is a need to re-investigate the data and perspectives on this area to look that how the nature of fight took shape and changes with the contemporary development outside the territory of Jharkhand.

With the formation of congress, and passing of the leadership under Gandhi a drastic shift occurred in Jharkhand. Before 1912 mostly the leaders of Jharkhand were fighting for their on rights and they were also not so popular. Their appeal to people were limited to grants of rights, but with the coming of national leaders their demand and way of protest was changed. To many extents this was one of the primary contributions done by national leaders, which gave a new life to the oldest fighting spirit of India- the Jharkhandi's. The freedom fighters of Bengal contributed in increasing dimensions of Jharkhand movement against the alien rule. Most of the young Bengali revolutionaries were used to take shelter in different area of Jharkhand when the British tried to crack them down. Nirmal Banerjee of Hazaribagh created his hideout in the area when in 1913 he pasted the handbill for freedom at various palaces.

During the extremist phase of congress Ganesh Chandra Gosh was one of the important revolutionaries on whom very little attention was paid by mainstream historians. The revolutionaries of Jharkhand were in close touch with their counterpart in Bengal and Maharashtra. Sachindra kumar sen once visited Ranchi and stayed for a long time at Doranda.

During Non-cooperation movement Ranchi and Hazaribagh was the prime centre. Gulab Tiwary, Ram Brahmachari, Nagarmal Modi, Swami Biswanand was some of the important congress from non-tribal group. Under Gandhian leadership another achievement was that now many leaders came from tribal group and played their role as a mainstream leader. At Hazaribagh, St. Columba's college was prime place for freedom struggle and students were involved actively during non-cooperation and Quit India movement. Ram Vinod Singh popularly nicknamed as '*jatin bagha*' was one of the important student leaders from Jharkhand on whom very less historical work was done.

During salt satyagraha in April 1930, the surrounding of several parts of Jharkhand was full of energy. At several places in Jharkhand broke the salt law. The British followed the repressive policy towards the satyagraha all over India. Krishna Ballabh Sahay broke the salt law by making salt near Khanzanchi tank in Hazaribagh. Naini Gopal led the Civil Disobedience Movement in Jamshedpur. Several public meetings, hartals, bandh was happened in Jharkhand, but again very less was known to the history books. By September 1930 nearly 137 freedom fighters were arrested in Hazaribagh. Two of the prominent leaders of Jharkhand tribal group Mopna Manjhi and Ketan Mehta were died which caused a widespread protest in Jharkhand.

Neta Ji, Ramgarh Congress Session and Santhal Pargana: One of the important congress session was held in Jharkhand on 18-20 March 1940, due to the initiative of Ram Narayan Singh and Dr. Rajinder prasad. This was an important event because this created the base of Quit India Movement of 1942. To prepare for the Ramgarh congress session Neta ji started Bihar Jan-Sam Park program and came to several area of Santhal Pargana. And from latter onward Subhash Chandra Bose also took the side path from congress. In the one side congress organized the session at the bank of Jhanda Chowk on the bank of Harhari river of Ramgarh and on the other side Neta ji started a parallel session to appeal the young blood of Jharkhand. Due to the ideological conflict with congress, he started Shobha yatra.

The president of *Freedom Fighter Organization Of Deoghar*, Late Baikunth Nath Jha wrote in '*Matribandhan Mukti-Sangram Mei Santhal Pargana*' that while preparing for the Ramgarh congress session Neta ji visited Mihirjam and stayed at the home of Dr. P. Banerjee. He appealed to the people and said that 'congress session was going to be held at Ramgarh, participate in that and decide what is going to be the nature of our freedom? British were not our friend they are our enemy and we can't trust them.

After Mihirjam he visited Madhupur, where many national leaders came later. Madhupur is also one of the forgotten areas in the books of history, where Neta ji gave fiery speech to the locals and women with special attention and organised them for upcoming events. From Madhupur he visited several other places including Brahmananda Dham and Ramakrishna Mission Vidyapith in Deoghar, Purana mina bazar, Dumka etc. Along with him several prominent persons of this area were together like Vibhuti Ghosh, Swami Gyanantmanand Maharaj, Advocate

Surendernath barman, Pandit Ramraj jajwade, Gauri Shankar Newar and so on.

Conclusion: Several prominent leaders visited Jharkhand during the National freedom movement and that is not my primary concern. The primary concern here is to point out those figures who worked hard together with national leader's but they got no place or a very little space in the history books. The concern and question are that was the freedom possible ever without the ground work and support of those grounded personalities? It is a need of hour to Revisit the Jharkhand history not as a regional history but as a national history on equal footing. Because there is no national history without the contribution of regional history. The work and sacrifices done by the people of Jharkhand state contain many thoughts in themselves, which needs to be recognized across the country.

References:

- <https://ramgarh.nic.in/history/>
- Soren, Shibu, ed S. Narayan (1992). Jharkhand Rajya Ka Sawal (The Question of Jharkhand Movement: Origin and Evolution, New Delhi.
- Roy, S.C, (1912). The Munda's And Their Country, Calcutta
- Jha, J.C, (1964). The Kol Insurrection In Chotanagpur, Calcutta
- Singh, Dr. Sunil Kumar 6th ed. (2015). Inside Jharkhand, Ranchi
- Kumar. Umesh, (2021,23 January). 'संथाल परगना की सरजमी और सरफरोश सुभाष', प्रभात खबर, Deoghar
- Uttam, Dr. Piyush, (2021,23 January). मधुपुर में नेताजी ने बजाया था आजादी का उद्घोष, प्रभात खबर, Deoghar

